

Depth-integrated marine ecosystem classification for Europe

Deliverable 2.5

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.5 overview

The present document details the data acquisition and computational procedures involved in Deliverable 2.5 of MPA Europe. It provides a **depth-integrated marine ecosystem classification for Europe** (0-2,500 m depth) using a wide range of spatially complete and standardised environmental data that reflect both ecosystem conditions and functioning.

The classification of ecosystems considered clustering algorithms fitting high-resolution environmental data for European seas (Environmental data preparation; Deliverable 2.1, WP2; Assis et al, 2023). In this scope and for the purposes of the MPA Europe project, ‘ecosystems’ are defined as “**enduring, spatially bounded environments where biological and energy interactions are greater within than with other ecosystems**” (Zhao et al. 2019). The information provided contributes to policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, mapping biodiversity patterns at an ecosystem level. It will feed the main subsequent tasks of Prioritisation (WP5), which aim to design (prioritise locations for) MPA networks using a systematic conservation planning approach maximising the coverage of the marine biodiversity.

Methods

The environmental data used in cluster analysis were derived from [Deliverable 2.1](#) (Assis et al., 2023). These data comprise environmental data layers with a 0.25 degrees resolution (approx. 27 km at the equator) for European seas. They are spatially complete and standardised, generated with information from the Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast and the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast, which are two pre-processed re-analyses of [Copernicus Marine Service](#) that integrate and assimilate a comprehensive range of satellite and in-situ data (Assis et al., 2023).

Nine meaningful environmental variables for the waters of European seas were selected. Eight of them were also used for surface waters ([Deliverable 2.3](#), Campoy et al., 2023a), namely, dissolved molecular oxygen (mmol m⁻³), nitrate (mmol m⁻³), ocean temperature (°C), pH, phosphate (mmol m⁻³), phytoplankton (mmol m⁻³), salinity and sea ice cover (%). The mixed layer depth (m) was also included for this analysis. Data were represented as the averaged values over the decade 2010-2019, except the sea ice cover, for which the maximum value for the 2010-2019 period was used. Thus, the ecosystem classification reflects the long-term enduring climatology that drives the distribution of species and habitats as distinct from seasonal and annual variation that affect population abundance.

To carry out a depth-integrated (three-dimensional) approach, 14 data layers were included for each environmental variable, corresponding to depths from 0 to 2,500 m (0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250, 500, 750, 1,000, 1,500, 2,000 and 2,500 m depth). In the case of sea ice cover, only a data layer for the 0 m depth was included, while for other depths, it was set to zero. On the other hand, the mixed layer depth was modified to follow the depth-integration format of the rest of the variables. Thus, cells above the mixed layer were assigned a zero value, while cells below the mixed layer were assigned a value of one. The correlation among selected variables was assessed through the Pearson's correlation coefficient (Table 1).

Table 1. Pearson's correlation coefficient for the nine environmental variables selected: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (temp), pH, phosphate (phosph), phytoplankton (phyto), salinity, sea ice cover (sea ice) and mixed layer depth (mixed).

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp	pH	Phosph	Phyto	Salinity	Sea ice	Mixed
Oxygen	1	0.05	-0.64	-0.02	-0.36	0.26	-0.17	0.22	-0.29
Nitrate		1	-0.60	-0.60	0.25	-0.59	0.07	-0.04	0.32
Temp			1	0.07	-0.28	0.26	0.24	-0.16	-0.08
pH				1	0.34	0.21	-0.12	0.10	-0.17
Phosph					1	-0.26	-0.46	-0.03	0.21
Phyto						1	-0.24	0.11	-0.59
Salinity							1	-0.13	0.02
Sea ice								1	-0.21
Mixed									1

Data were standardised using Z-scores. This procedure involved adjusting each data point to be centred on the mean and scaled based on the standard deviation. Standardisation with Z-scores is necessary for removing scale bias, ensuring an unbiased interpretation of results, and facilitating comparisons between variables.

Following a similar approach developed for the classifications of marine ecosystem in Europe for surface ([Deliverable 2.3](#), Campoy et al. 2023a) and near seabed waters ([Deliverable 2.4](#), Campoy et al. 2023b), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was further performed to mitigate inter-variable correlations and reduce data dimensionality. PCA is a multivariate technique that transforms the original variables into a new set of orthogonal variable dimensions called principal components. The initial six principal components were selected, which collectively explained 95 % of the variance in the data (Table 2). By retaining these components, information was effectively captured while reducing the complexity of the dataset.

Table 2. Result of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The first six principal components (PC1-6) recovered 95 % of the variance in the data matrix (in **bold**).

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9
Standard deviation	1.59	1.41	1.30	0.94	0.90	0.80	0.51	0.25	0.19
Proportion of variance	0.28	0.22	0.19	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.00
Cumulative proportion	0.28	0.50	0.69	0.79	0.88	0.95	0.98	0.99	1.00

The PCA led to a data matrix comprising 272,187 rows (i.e., linked to the 0.25 resolution cells) and six columns (i.e., PC1-6). The dataset underwent normalization by scaling each variable to a range between 0 and 1 (Figure 1). This preprocessing step ensured that variables with different scales contributed equally to subsequent analyses. By eliminating the influence of variable scales, the normalized data provides a foundation for accurate and meaningful interpretations, especially when employing algorithms sensitive to input feature magnitudes, such as clustering and distance-based methods.

Figure 1. Variable distribution in the dataset before clustering. Each of the six variables corresponds to a principal component (PC1-6) preserved after PCA.

The k-means clustering approach was utilised to find structure in the data. This is a popular unsupervised machine learning algorithm used for partitioning a dataset into a predefined number of distinct, non-overlapping clusters. It works by iteratively assigning data points to the nearest cluster centroid and then recalculating the centroids based on the mean of the points assigned to each cluster. This process continues until convergence when the centroids no longer change significantly. Thus, it

is suitable for clustering data points with numerical features into k clusters, where k is a user-specified parameter. It is an efficient method known for its simplicity in cluster assignment.

K-means algorithms seek to minimise the within-cluster sum of squared (WSS) distances, i.e., between each data point and the centroid of its assigned cluster, while maximising the between-cluster sum of squared (BSS) distances, i.e. between the centroids of all clusters and the overall mean of the data. The total sum of squares ($TSS=WSS+BSS$) represents the total variability in the data without considering the clustering. WSS, BSS and TSS are metrics used to evaluate the performance and quality of the clustering.

One important aspect of clustering, including the k-means approach, is the specification of the number of clusters (k). To achieve this, there is a range of options from which the user may choose. One unified approach is to combine these solutions using the *NbClust* library (Charrad et al. 2014) of R computing language (R Core Team, 2023). It implements and compares 30 cluster validity indices to provide the best clustering structure consensus from a range of results. Due to the substantial size of the dataset and the *NbClust* requirement to compute a distance matrix, resource limitation prevented from executing the function for the entire dataset. Instead, 100 random samples of a size of 10,000 were iteratively generated to calculate the validity indices. A dissimilarity matrix was computed for each 10,000-size subset using Euclidean distances to test up to 20 possible clusters. The outcome derived from the combination of indices, indicated that **two clusters** is the optimal choice to structure the data, followed by **eight clusters** (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Optimal number of clusters according to the combined outcome of 30 cluster validity indices obtained from 100 random samples of 10,000 data points. $k=2$ was selected more often (Count) across indices and samples.

However, the optimal clustering solution ($k=2$ in this case) may not align with the requirements of the clustering process, as it might be considered either too general or too specific. To address this

challenge, we have chosen to implement a **divisive hierarchical k-means** approach. In this approach, $k=2$ is initially specified, and after running the algorithm, we iterate it for the cluster with the higher WSS. This process can be repeated until all clusters represent individual cells, resulting in the number of clusters (k) being equal to the number of observations in the data matrix.

The hierarchical k-means clustering was applied to the data using the *kmeans* function from the R package *stats* (R Core Team 2023), utilising the Lloyd's algorithm. This algorithm is a three-step approach to minimize the WSS. It starts by choosing two random data points as centroids ($k=2$) on each iteration. Then, it assigns all data points to their closest centroid, and finally it performs the recalculation of centroids as mean over all their assigned data points. These last two steps are repeated until the defined maximum of 500 iterations. Since the resulting clusters are heavily influenced by the choosing of initial centroids, i.e., the Lloyd's algorithm might get stuck in a local optimum, 100 random initial centroid assignments were allowed.

The above-described approach is known as a **hard partition** because the cluster membership is strict, i.e., each data point belongs to a single cluster. The alternative is a **fuzzy partition**, where every data point has a probability of closeness (in a range of 0 to 1) to each cluster. This approach is more realistic than hard partition since data points can belong to multiple clusters with varying degrees of likelihood, allowing for the representation of uncertainty and overlapping patterns in the cluster assignments. To incorporate fuzzy partition in the analyses, the fuzzy c-means algorithm was implemented through the *cmeans* function of the R package *e1071* (Meyer et al. 2023). On each step of the divisive hierarchical approach, the fuzzy probabilities of each data point were recalculated for the full dataset and the new cluster assignments.

The clustering quality was inferred using four independent metrics: Silhouette Score, Dunn Index, Entropy and Cluster Stability. These metrics, detailed in Table 3, capture different aspects of cluster quality, providing a comprehensive understanding of the resulting structure. Due to computational resource limitations imposed by the dataset size, random samples of size 10,000 were iteratively generated to calculate the Silhouette Score, Dunn Index and Entropy. Additionally, the significance of these metrics was evaluated through bootstrapping, comparing the metrics of each sample to the distribution obtained from 100 permutations. This method determines the proportion of randomly generated clustering metrics that are equal to or greater than the actual values. A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was used to determine statistical significance. For Cluster Stability, the data were resampled 100 times using bootstrap and the Jaccard similarities of the original clusters to the most similar clusters in the resampled data computed. These metrics are available in the R package *fpc* (Hennig 2023).

Table 3. Summary of clustering validation metrics.

Metric	Description	Interpretation
Silhouette Score	It measures how similar an object is to its own cluster (intra-cluster similarity) compared to other clusters (inter-cluster dissimilarity). It is calculated as the average silhouette coefficient for all points in the dataset, providing a way to assess the quality of clustering by quantifying the compactness and separation of the clusters.	It ranges from -1 to 1. A score closer to +1 indicates that the clustering configuration is appropriate, with well-defined clusters. Conversely, a score near -1 suggests that the clustering may have been inappropriate, with points possibly assigned to the wrong clusters. A score around 0 indicates overlapping clusters or points at the decision boundary between clusters.
Dunn Index	It evaluates the compactness of clusters (intra-cluster distance) relative to the separation between clusters (inter-cluster distance). It is calculated as the ratio of the minimum inter-cluster distance to the maximum intra-cluster distance.	It theoretically ranges from 0 to infinity, however, values from 0 to 1 are more common. A higher value suggests better clustering, with smaller intra-cluster distances and larger inter-cluster distances, suggesting well-separated and compact clusters. Conversely, a lower Dunn index suggests less optimal clustering, with clusters that are either spread out or too close together.
Entropy	It measures the homogeneity or heterogeneity within clusters by calculating the distribution of class labels or attributes within each cluster. It quantifies the degree of uncertainty in cluster assignments based on the diversity of data points within clusters.	It ranges from 0 to 1, where lower values indicate higher homogeneity and higher values indicate higher heterogeneity within clusters. A low entropy value suggests that most data points within a cluster belong to the same class or share similar attribute values, indicating well-defined and internally consistent clusters. Conversely, a high entropy value indicates that data points within a cluster are diverse in terms of class labels or attribute values, suggesting less coherent clusters with unclear boundaries.
Cluster Stability	It assesses the robustness of clustering solutions by measuring the sensitivity of cluster assignments to variations in the input data. It quantifies the degree of variation in cluster memberships when the data is perturbed or resampled.	The Jaccard similarity index ranges from 0 to 1. In the context of cluster stability assessment, values closer to 1 indicate more stable clusters, while lower values closer to 0 suggest higher cluster instability. Jaccard values between 0.6 and 0.75 suggest potential patterns but uncertain assignments. Below 0.6, clusters lack reliability. Valid clusters aim for Jaccard values of 0.75 or higher, with "highly stable" clusters surpassing 0.85.

Results

The divisive hierarchical k-means approach produced a reduction in the overall WSS and an augmentation in the global BSS, with the TSS remaining constant throughout the process (Table 4).

Table 4. Result for the first 10 levels of clustering using the divisive hierarchical k-means implementation. The number of clusters (*N. Clusters*) increases one unit in each iteration. TSS: Total sum of Squares. WSS: Within Sum of Squares. BSS: Between Sum of Squares.

Level	N. Clusters	TSS	WSS	BSS
1	2	12,941.12	10,077.11	2,864.01
2	3	12,941.12	8,452.93	4,488.19
3	4	12,941.12	7,708.18	5,232.95
4	5	12,941.12	6,197.92	6,743.21
5	6	12,941.12	4,612.70	8,328.43
6	7	12,941.12	3,483.02	9,458.10
7	8	12,941.12	2,964.77	9,976.35
8	9	12,941.12	2,460.61	10,480.52
9	10	12,941.12	2,284.16	10,656.97
10	11	12,941.12	2,144.20	10,796.93

This can also be observed in Figure 3. On each step, the cluster with the higher WSS is subdivided, causing a decreasing in the WSS and an increasing in both the number of clusters and the overall BSS.

Figure 3. TSS (Total Sum of Squares, red dashed line), WSS (Within Sum of Squares) and BSS (Between Sum of Squares) for the first 100 levels of clustering using the divisive hierarchical k-means implementation. The number of clusters increases one unit in each iteration resulting in 101 clusters.

As clusters are subdivided, they appear environmentally closer. The relationship between clusters as well as the environmental distance among them is represented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Environmental Euclidean distance between 101 clusters after the first 100 levels of clustering using the divisive hierarchical *k*-means implementation.

Maximum fuzzy probabilities (i.e., the maximum probability of each data point to belong to a specific cluster) varied from 0.12 to 1, with a median of 0.76 across depths of European seas. The distribution of these values slightly varied across hierarchical levels (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Maximum fuzzy probabilities for the first 10 levels of clustering using the divisive hierarchical *k*-means implementation. The line inside the box represents the median (50th percentile) of the data. The lower (Q1) and upper (Q3) edges of the box correspond to the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. The whiskers extend 1.5 times the interquartile range.

The clustering validation metrics for the first 10 levels are presented in Table 5. The Silhouette Score consistently yielded positive values (>0.28), suggesting a well-performing clustering configuration. Moreover, these values exhibited an increasing trend from Level 1 to Levels 7-8, indicating reduced overlap among clusters at these deeper levels. However, the Dunn Index values approaching zero suggest that the clusters lack compactness and clear differentiation, which is unsurprising given the complexity of the data. Entropy values, on the other hand, did not show significance beyond Level 3, implying that they are not significantly different from those expected by random chance, rendering them meaningless. Interestingly, for the initial three levels, the entropy values increased, reflecting growing heterogeneity attributable to the complexity of the data. Furthermore, the Cluster Stability analysis revealed high stability for clustering solutions across Levels 1-7 (Jaccard>0.75), underscoring the suitability of the chosen parameters in the k-means clustering algorithm, including the maximum number of iterations allowed and random initializations.

Table 5. Results of four clustering validation metrics. The significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) of the Silhouette Score, Dunn Index, and Entropy is highlighted with an asterisk (). The Cluster Stability result corresponds to the range of cluster-specific values.*

Level	N. Clusters	Silhouette Score	Dunn Index	Entropy	Cluster Stability
1	2	0.28*	0.00*	0.67*	1.00
2	3	0.31*	0.00*	0.82*	0.89-1.00
3	4	0.28*	0.00*	1.10*	1.00
4	5	0.37*	0.00*	1.47	0.97-1.00
5	6	0.38*	0.00*	1.51	1.00
6	7	0.40*	0.00*	1.54	0.97-1.00
7	8	0.42*	0.00*	1.66	1.00
8	9	0.43*	0.00*	1.68	0.73-1.00
9	10	0.37*	0.00*	1.90	0.40-1.00
10	11	0.35*	0.00*	2.05	0.25-1.00

Level 1

Maximum fuzzy probabilities for the hierarchical Level 1 varied from 0.50 to 0.95, with a median of 0.76 across depths of European seas. This hierarchical level revealed that surface waters (0 m depth) were less resolved since they present lower assignment probabilities (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Maximum fuzzy probabilities across depths for the hierarchical Level 1 of clustering using the divisive hierarchical *k*-means implementation. The line inside the box represents the median (50th percentile) of the data. The lower (*Q1*) and upper (*Q3*) edges of the box correspond to the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. The whiskers extend 1.5 times the interquartile range.

Both the hard and fuzzy partitions for Level 1 are represented in Figure 7. In surface waters, Cluster 1 (blue) spans the Mediterranean Sea and the adjacent Northeast Atlantic Ocean, including the Azores Islands. On the other hand, Cluster 2 (pink) defines the Northeast Atlantic, Celtic Sea, North Sea, Baltic Sea, Black Sea, and some upwelling or colder regions along the Moroccan, Iberian, French Atlantic, northeast Adriatic, and Greek coasts. Cluster 2 becomes smaller with depth, while Cluster 1 expands into northern areas of the Atlantic Ocean. Cluster 1 even completely spans the Black Sea at 500 m depth. However, in deeper waters (2,500 m depth, Figure 7n), Cluster 1 is restricted to the Mediterranean, while Cluster 2 spans the entire Atlantic area at this depth. The fuzzy partition reveals that the areas with higher uncertainty at 0 m depth are in the North Atlantic, around the Celtic Sea, the upwelling zones, and the Baltic and Black seas. Nevertheless, this situation changes significantly with depth. Interestingly, at 75-250 m depth, this uncertainty is mainly concentrated around Sweden, Norway, and Iceland, together with the Baltic and Black seas. Although the Black Sea belongs to both clusters in its entirety, the uncertainty remains high across depths (Figure 7). This may be an indication of very distinct environmental characteristics from both clusters.

Figure 7. European marine ecosystems classification estimated by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions through k-means clustering analysis of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 5 km wide (0.05 degrees) for representation. All depths from 0 to 2,500 m included in the clustering are represented (a-n). Colour scale defines the two distinctive clusters (pink and blue) identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

The two clusters result of Level 1 were linked to distinct environmental characteristics (Figure 8; Table 6). Cluster 1 exhibits relatively lower levels of dissolved molecular oxygen compared to Cluster 2, with a wider range indicating variability across zones. Nitrate concentrations are lower in Cluster 1 compared to Cluster 2, with substantial variability in both clusters. Ocean temperature in Cluster 1 ranges from 6.37 to 23.7 °C, indicating a moderate temperature range, while Cluster 2 experiences a wider temperature range (-1.80 to 19.2 °C). Both clusters maintain similar pH levels around 8.05, with minor fluctuations. Phosphate levels are lower in Cluster 1. Phytoplankton levels also exhibit some differences, with slightly higher values in Cluster 2 than in Cluster 1. Salinity levels are higher in Cluster 1 than in Cluster 2, with a narrower range. Notably, sea ice cover above zero are in Cluster 2. Overall, Cluster 1 tends to have lower oxygen, nitrate, and phosphate levels but higher salinity compared to Cluster 2, which experiences broader temperature and nitrate ranges.

Figure 8. Environmental characteristics of the two identified clusters in the hierarchical Level 1. Eight variables: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (tem), pH, phosphate, phytoplankton (phyto), salinity and sea ice cover (sea.ice). The mixed layer depth is not represented for being binary. Mean of each variable in red and range (minimum and maximum) in yellow. It is important to note that the values are presented in percentages, where 0-100 % represents the full range of each variable. This approach ensures comparability among the clusters.

Table 6. Summary of the environmental characteristics of the two identified clusters. Eight variables: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (temp.), pH, phosphate (phosph), phytoplankton (phyto), salinity, and sea ice cover (sea ice). Mean of each variable and range [min, max].

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp.	pH	Phosph	Phyto	Salinity	Sea ice
Cluster 1	210 [0.25- 289]	5.78 [0- 33.5]	14.8 [6.37, 23.7]	8.05 [7.72, 8.38]	0.57 [0.00, 8.46]	0.48 [0.01, 6.92]	36.6 [19.2, 40.0]	0 [0, 0]
Cluster 2	298 [167- 409]	9.65 [0.01- 27.5]	4.40 [- 1.80, 19.2]	8.05 [7.29, 8.30]	0.75 [0.00, 3.40]	0.63 [0.01, 18.8]	33.9 [1.89, 36.6]	0.02 [0- 0.97]

Level 7

Maximum fuzzy probabilities for the hierarchical Level 7 varied from 0.16 to 1, with a median of 0.76 across depths of European seas. This hierarchical level revealed that deeper waters (> 1,500 m depth) were less resolved since they presented decreased assignment probabilities (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Maximum fuzzy probabilities across depths for the hierarchical Level 7 of clustering using the divisive hierarchical k -means implementation. The line inside the box represents the median (50th percentile) of the data. The lower ($Q1$) and upper ($Q3$) edges of the box correspond to the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. The whiskers extend 1.5 times the interquartile range.

Both the hard and fuzzy partitions for Level 7 are depicted in Figure 10. A notable observation at this level is that not all clusters are present across all depths. Specifically, only Clusters 1-5 (depicted in blue, pink, orange, light blue, and green, respectively, in Figure 10a) are observed in surface waters. Notably, Cluster 1 is absent below the surface. Conversely, Clusters 6 and 7 (illustrated in yellow and purple, respectively, in Figure 10b-n) are exclusively observed below 25 meters across all depths. Additionally, Cluster 8 (represented in red, Figure 10f-m) is only evident below a depth of 150 meters, primarily characterizing the Black Sea region partially or entirely at these depths. The level of fuzziness is markedly different from Level 1. At Level 7, higher fuzziness closely aligns with the cluster boundaries, suggesting that: (1) the boundaries between clusters are dynamic, and (2) the clusters are more precisely delineated, as evidenced by the absence of areas with high fuzziness, such as the Black Sea in Level 1, across various depths.

Figure 10. European marine ecosystems classification estimated by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions through *k*-means clustering analysis of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 10 km wide (0.05 degrees) for representation. All depths from 0 to 2,500 m included in the clustering are represented (a-n). Colour scale defines the eight distinctive clusters (from 1 to 8: blue, pink, orange, light blue, green, yellow, purple, and red) identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

The eight identified clusters exhibit diverse environmental characteristics (Figure 11; Table 7). Thus, Cluster 1 demonstrates relatively high oxygen levels and moderate nitrate concentrations, with a narrow temperature range suggesting stable conditions. In contrast, Cluster 2 exhibits lower oxygen levels but higher nitrate concentrations and a wider temperature range, indicating more variable conditions. Cluster 3 shows high oxygen levels and moderate nitrate concentrations, with a wider temperature range compared to Cluster 1 but narrower than Cluster 2. Cluster 4, similar to Cluster 1, displays moderate oxygen levels and nitrate concentrations, with a narrower temperature range. Cluster 5 is characterized by lower oxygen levels and minimal nitrate concentrations but experiences high temperatures. Cluster 6, with moderate oxygen levels and relatively high nitrate concentrations, displays extreme temperature ranges, possibly indicating polar or equatorial regions. Cluster 7 demonstrates moderate oxygen and nitrate levels, with temperatures similar to Cluster 1 but a wider range. Finally, Cluster 8 exhibits significantly lower oxygen and nitrate levels but higher phosphate

concentrations and lower pH, suggesting unique environmental conditions. These variations underscore the diversity of environmental factors influencing each cluster's characteristics.

Figure 11. Environmental characteristics of the eight identified clusters in the hierarchical Level 7. Eight variables: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (tem), pH, phosphate, phytoplankton (phyto), salinity and sea ice cover (sea.ice). The mixed layer depth is not represented. Mean of each variable in red and range (minimum and maximum) in yellow. It is important to note that the values are presented in percentages, where 0-100 % represents the full range of each variable. This approach ensures comparability among the clusters.

Table 7. Summary of the environmental characteristics of the eight identified clusters. Eight variables: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (temp), pH, phosphate (phosph), phytoplankton (phyto), salinity, and sea ice cover (sea ice). Mean of each variable and range [min, max].

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp	pH	Phosph	Phyto	Salinity	Sea ice
Cluster 1	358.10 [296.36, 383.05]	6.53 [0.58, 16.55]	0.55 [- 1.80, 10.23]	8.10 [7.29, 8.17]	0.47 [0.02, 0.63]	1.17 [0.37, 5.87]	30.75 [1.89, 35.60]	0.88 [0.47, 0.97]
Cluster 2	296.31 [166.85, 371.77]	7.53 [0.13, 27.46]	6.71 [- 1.72, 19.23]	8.07 [7.86, 8.24]	0.55 [0.00, 2.17]	1.21 [0.01, 16.22]	35.00 [22.80, 36.61]	0.01 [0, 0.55]

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp	pH	Phosph	Phyto	Salinity	Sea ice
Cluster 3	302.05 [169.24, 408.67]	1.57 [0.01, 9.66]	8.75 [2.61, 18.45]	8.11 [7.39, 8.30]	1.59 [0.01, 3.40]	1.70 [0.09, 18.78]	14.06 [3.02, 31.09]	0.01 [0, 0.54]
Cluster 4	295.43 [175.09, 371.67]	11.60 [0.13, 20.19]	2.91 [- 1.71, 18.20]	8.04 [7.32, 8.15]	0.81 [0.01, 1.53]	0.20 [0.01, 6.28]	34.93 [10.78, 36.33]	0.00 [0, 0.01]
Cluster 5	234.70 [212.99, 275.09]	0.22 [0.00, 3.71]	19.53 [12.71, 23.70]	8.06 [8.02, 8.16]	0.03 [0.00, 0.79]	1.25 [0.72, 6.92]	37.19 [31.10, 40.03]	0 [0, 0]
Cluster 6	201.77 [83.02, 288.59]	12.67 [0.19, 33.51]	201.77 [83.02, 288.59]	7.99 [7.72, 8.28]	0.88 [0.01, 3.77]	0.16 [0.01, 4.02]	35.53 [19.19, 38.56]	0 [0, 0]
Cluster 7	218.90 [73.38, 289.32]	3.06 [0.00, 9.91]	15.84 [9.10, 23.62]	8.08 [8.00, 8.26]	0.19 [0.00, 4.50]	0.49 [0.01, 3.75]	37.89 [34.07, 39.96]	0 [0,0]
Cluster 8	21.22 [0.25, 143.49]	0.66 [0.00, 4.88]	8.83 [8.50, 13.59]	8.35 [8.23, 8.38]	6.77 [3.73, 8.46]	0.02 [0.02, 0.12]	22.13 [20.63, 38.96]	0 [0, 0]

Conclusions

In summary, by selecting biologically meaningful environmental variables and applying k-means clustering analysis using a newly implemented hierarchical approach, the current deliverable offers a robust depth-integrated classification of marine ecosystems in European sea-surface waters. Level 7 reveals eight well-defined clusters, each associated with distinct environmental characteristics. These clusters offer valuable insights for policymakers and researchers, especially concerning MPA designation and biodiversity conservation and will be used for the prioritisation analyses. The rigorous validation metrics demonstrate the quality and reliability of the clustering results, further underscoring their significance for the objectives of the MPA Europe project.

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